

NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY 2020 AND HIGHER EDUCATION

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Introduction:

Nelson Mandela says that Education is the most powerful weapon which you can use to change the world. National Education Commission popularly known as Kothari Commission was an advoc commission set up by the Government of India to examine all aspects of the educational sector on India to evolve a general pattern of education and to advice guidelines and policies for the development of education in India.

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Mahatma Phule was fully conscious about the importance of education as a tool of social justice and equality. In fact he saw education as the harbinger of a social revolution. The essence of the educational philosophy of Mahatma phule was that education is a human right.

Higher education plays an important role in development of the country. Higher education has contributed sustaintically to their socio-economic, political and cultural development. It supplies man power required by industry, agricultural, science and technology and services, as such the objectives of self-reliant economy can be achieved only when professionals, managers, technicians are available plan and research activities. Hence expenditure on education particularly on higher education has been regarded as an important investment. The return on investment in higher education has been considerably high because of its contribution to human resource development. So New Education Policy 2020 set clear targets for higher education.

Objectives of study:

- 1) To study the present position of higher education.
- 2) To study the education policy of 1986.
- 3) To study the New Education Policy 2020
- 4) To study comparative analysis of education policy of 1986 and New Education policy 2020.

Research Methodology:

A researcher has used secondary data collected from various books, journals, magazines, and publications, websites. etc.

Hypothesis:

- 1) Present position of higher education is very difficult.
- 2) Implementation of the education policy of 1986 not succeed.
- 3) New Education policy 2020 ensurity equitable access to quality education to all students.

National policy on education 1986

The system of education in India has been undergone changes from time to time. But it has been adequately realistic and related to the life. The NPE 1986 has rightly said, “The country has reached a stage in its economic and technical development when a major effort must be made to derive to maximum benefit from the assets already created and to ensure that the fruits of change reach all sections. Education is highway to this goal, with this objective the government of India announced in January 1985 that a new education policy would be formulated for the country.

Features of this policy:

- 1) The common educational structure 10+2+3 has been accepted in all parts of the country.
- 2) Education for women SC, ST, Handicapped, Minority communities etc.
- 3) Adult education and continuously education would be provided through various media and programs
- 4) Development of young child, particularly children from sections of the population in which first generation learners.
- 5) In view of the need to effect and all round improvement in the situations of higher education. It is proposed that in the near future.
- 6) The Open University system has been initiated in order to augment opportunities for higher education and as an instrument of democratizing education
- 7) A beginning will be degrees from jobs in selected area. The proposal however cannot be applied to occupation. Specific courses like engineering, medicine, law, teaching etc.
- 8) Research as a means of renovation and renewal of education process will be under taken by all higher technical institutions.
- 9) Work experience viewed as purposive and meaningful manual work organized as an integral part of the learning process.
- 10) The status of the teacher reflects the socio-cultural ethos of society.
- 11) Teacher education is a continuous process and its pre services and in service components are inseparable. As the first step, the system of teacher education will be overhauled.
- 12) State level and district level, Advisory Boards of education may be set up for taking effective measures for better interactions and management of education at various stages.

National Education Policy 2020:

Education is fundamental for achieving full human potential developing and equitable a just society and promoting national development providing universal access to quality education is the key to India’s continued ascent and leadership on the global stage in terms of economic growth, social justice and equality, scientific advancement, national integration and cultural preservations. Universal high quality education is the best way forward for developing and maximizing our country rich talent and resources for the good of the individual, the society, the country and the world.

Vision of this policy:

This policy envisions an education system rooted in Indian ethos that contributes directly to transforming India. Providing high quality education to all and thereby making India a global knowledge superpower. The vision of policy is to instill, among the learners a deep rooted pride n being Indian, not only in thought but also in spirit, intellect and deeds as well as to develop knowledge skills, values and dispositions that support responsible commitment to human rights, sustainable development and living and global well being thereby reflecting a truly global citizen.

Steps to be taken by government

- i) Enhance gender balance in admissions to higher education
- ii) Establishing higher quality special education zone in higher education.
- iii) Develop and support high quality higher education that teaches in local and Indian language.
- iv) Provide more financial assistance and scholarships to public and private colleges.
- v) Develop and support technology tools for better participation and learning outcomes.
- vi) Admission processes more inclusive.
- vii) Developed the effective governance and leadership that enables the creations of a culture of excellence and innovation in higher education institutions.
- viii) All leadership positions and Heads of institutions will be offered to persons with high academic qualifications.

Suggestions:

- 1) Improvement of standards and quality of education.
- 2) Removal of social disparities and regional imbalances in higher educational facilities.
- 3) Restructuring of courses including developing a career trust in the courses.
- 4) Grant of autonomous status to qualifying colleges.
- 5) Develop the innovation program like that vocational/career oriented programs. Quality of life improvement program, leadership and human resource development program.
- 6) The focus on area studies program.
- 7) Development of engineering/ technology and management education.
- 8) Facilities provides for SC/ST/OBC and handicapped and weaker sections.
- 9) Assistance is provided by the UGC to universities and colleges for setting up centers and cells for women's studies.
- 10) Promotion and preservation of Indian culture, heritage and values.
- 11) The focus on human resource development with the skill development program specially staff development, Industry-institute interaction, continuing education, management, development, women in development, Environment development, student services, Equipment repair facility.

Conclusion:

It is hoped that successful implementation of the New Education Policy 2020 will be able to realize the educational system. The future of shape of education in India depends upon New Education Policy 2020. So Human resource development wit education playing its multi-dimensional role is now hopefully towards our education system.

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